

IMPORTANTCE OF UNDERSTANDING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the importance of understanding intercultural communication in business. Moreover, it highlightes why we need the strongest relationship between communication and culture in business sphere and the assumptions of the vast majority of linguistics from scientific side.

Key words: *communication, culture, business, intercultural communication, teaching, business English, verbal communication, non-verbal communication.*

Introduction. In the era of globalization of public relations, active introduction of information technologies in business, interpersonal communication practices and expanding international relations, it has been already become clearly that it is impossible to develop the country without professionals who know foreign languages perfectly, especially in business spheres. Obviously, international business activities always require communication with other cultures. Since there is a rapid increase in the globalization, all business activities, such as exchanging information, negotiating, so on and so forth are based on the ability to communicate with people whose cultural background is different. That's why it is essential to teach Business English not only from linguistic view but also from the cultural view. Even though business English has

been already investigated and has enough methods and approaches of its own, learners are encountering several problems including understanding the culture of other nations, usage of lexical meaning of the culture words and be aware of the differences in values and beliefs of other cultures.

Methodology

The term "Intercultural Communication" was first utilized by American anthropologist Edward T. Hall, who used it for the first time in his book *The Silent Language* in 1959. According to Hart (1998) the book is sometimes called "the field's founding document". Edward T. Hall was a staff member at the Foreign Service Institute prior to publishing the book, Michigan, USA (1951-1955), where he with his colleagues, dealt with what can be called the first original paradigm for Intercultural Communication. The most important parts and elements of Hall's paradigm for Intercultural Communication (Hart) were investigated by Hart(1998).

According to Lustig and Koester (2006, 46) "intercultural communication is a symbolic, interpretive, transactional, contextual process in which people from different cultures create shared meanings."

"Communication is a dialogue, not a monologue" (Notes Desk, March 11 2009) Communication is considered to be a process of delivering messages from one to another person through verbal and nonverbal communication. Kreitner and Carlene (2010) highlighted "The communication process is a chain made up of identifiable links. Links in this process include sender, encoding, medium, decoding, receiver and feedback."

Results

Accordingly, Hall's paradigm highlighted systematic empirical study and the classification of nonverbal communication which can be defined as communication that does not include the exchange of words. Secondly, emphasis, especially in nonverbal communication, on the out-of-conscious level of information-exchange and focus on intercultural communication, not as earlier on macro level monocultural studies have been identified. Thirdly, a non-judgmental view toward and acceptance of

cultural differences and participatory training methods in Intercultural Communication can be the main elements of Hall's paradigm.

The main aim of the Intercultural Communication was purposed to create practical purposes rather than for theoretical considerations: Training was the main and vital objective. American diplomats were the first target people of training and development of the people whose intercultural skills had to be increased.

The first trainings were held in the Foreign Service Institute and from this institute, Intercultural Communication teaching and training were applied for the universities and other organizations. Academic textbooks in Intercultural Communication begun appearing in the USA in a larger scale in the 1970 years after university courses had been taught. Those courses spread to Europe, therefore, in Europe, the first university courses in Intercultural Communication started taking places in the 1980 years. One of the famous pioneers universities was The University of Jyväskylä in Europe. From the beginning of the Intercultural communication, Intercultural Communication has been more applied focus on teaching and training. It has been investigated from the view of theory and theoretical sides have been matured as an academic field in the recent decades.

According to Kreitner and Carlene (2010) there are 5 steps to make communication process more effectively. They are:

Sender

Message

channel/medium

Receiver

Feedback

The idea will be developed by sender to be sent in the first place. This step can be planned as planning step where the speaker will choose the topic to communicate. Next step is encoding which converts the idea into a perceivable form of the speech such as formal letter, report form or complain letter, funeral speech, birthday wish so on and so forth. After the encoding has been finished, the sender can choose the different

ways to deliver the message, it can be oral, written or nonverbal. After then, The sender may choose a channel or medium to transmit the message to the receiver. The next step is transmitting the information and the sender's duty also ends with this step. Afterwards, the receiver will receive the message and start decoding it which means to understand. At this level, the importance of intercultural communication plays very important role since in order to make the communication to be effective, both a sender and a receiver have to have a common understanding or interest and be aware of intercultural exceptions. The last step is to give feedback or react. This step is considered to be extremely essential for a communication since it demonstrates how the receiver has understood the message correctly.

Discussion

It can be concluded that definition for Intercultural communication can be studying and understanding how people who have different cultural background communicate with each other. It helps to produce a guideline that helps people to communicate better with. Studies and researches conducted on intercultural communication usually begin from the differences and similarities between two distinct cultural groups then investigate the interaction between these groups.

Moreover, every culture has its own way and approach of delivering the message or information that they have. It is true that the way of communicating differs from one culture to another. Obviously, the differences which exist in communication between two cultures are mainly based on verbal and nonverbal signs and codes, social perceptions, cultural patterns, relationships standards and roles. When the differences between two cultures are relatively large, it may lead to lots of misinterpretation, misunderstanding and dissimilar expectations about how to have communication competently. That's way, the delivering the message to the people whose cultural background is different is much more difficult in intercultural communication.

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